

Studies on the Complexes of Fe(III), Co(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with Potassium *n*-Butyl Xanthate

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The reaction of several transitional metals with potassium *n*-butyl xanthate was studied by electrometric titrations and chemical analysis. The 1 : 2 complexes were formed with Fe(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) and a 1 : 3 complex in the case of Co(II). These complexes were subjected to spectral and magnetic studies in order to determine their structural characteristics. The magnetic moment studies provide evidence for the existence of an octahedral high spin xanthate complex in the case of Fe(III), an octahedral cobalt complex with cobalt in (III) oxidation state and Cu(II) and Ni(II) square planar complexes. Infrared spectra show that C-O-C is not involved in complex formation. On the other hand coordination with sulphur takes place as evinced by the shift in the C=S stretching bands. In case of Fe(III) complex there is evidence of H₂O being in the coordination sphere.

In comparison to other sulphur containing ligands, reaction of xanthates with metals have not been systematically studied. Metal xanthates are quite important as insecticides and fungicides, and they have found use in analytical separations. Comprehensive investigation on their composition and structural characteristics is therefore, very desirable.

Earlier studies were mostly limited to the elucidation of crystal parameters of nickel, cobalt and ferric ethyl xanthates. Physico-chemical studies on these complexes are of recent origin. Claudia and co-workers¹ have reported results of spectral studies on ferric potassium xanthates. Analytical studies were carried out by Rolando *et al*² for the separation of Ni(II), Co(II) ethyl xanthate complexes from zinc solution by solvent extraction technique and by Wilms *et al*³ for the micro determination of cobalt by potassium methyl xanthate.

The survey of the literature has shown that higher homologues of alkyl xanthates have not so far been used as ligands. It was therefore, thought worthwhile to carry out physico-chemical studies on the reactions of potassium *n*-butyl xanthate (henceforth abbreviated as PNBX) with some transitional metals. The results of these investigations are reported in this paper.

Experimental

Potassium *n*-butyl xanthate (PNBX) was prepared⁴ from *n*-butyl alcohol, carbon disulphide and KOH. The product was recrystallised from ethanol and petroleum ether (Found S=33.9%, calc. 34.0). The compound was characterised by i.r.

Air free double distilled conductivity water was used for preparing solutions throughout the experiments. Freshly prepared PNBX solution was always used. Stock solutions of nickel sulphate, cobalt chloride, ferric chloride and copper acetate were prepared by dissolving the B.D.H. 'AR' grade salt in conductivity water. Their strengths were determined by the usual methods.

Both direct and reverse conductometric titrations were performed to decide the composition of the metal Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II)-*n*-butyl xanthato-complexes. Phillips conductivity bridge with a dip type conductivity cell (cell constant 0.62) was used for conductance measurements.

Amperometric titrations were performed to confirm metal-ligand ratio using Toshniwal manual polarograph. Potassium chloride solution (2 M) was used as the supporting electrolyte and freshly prepared 0.2% solution of gelatin was used as maximum suppressor in all the cases. A constant potential of -0.3 volts vs SCE was selected from the plateau of PNBX for all the titrations except in case of Cu(II) where a potential of -0.1 V vs SCE was applied.

The following method was used for the isolation of the complexes :

250 ml of $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ of metal salts solutions were added to 500 ml of equimolecular solution of PNBX while for Co(II), the two solutions were mixed in the molar ratio 1 : 3. The dark brown, dark yellow, pale yellow and dark green xanthato-complexes of the respective metals got precipitated

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL RESULTS

Complex	% of metal		% of sulphur		% of Chlorine	
	Found	Requires	Found	Requires	Found	Requires
$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Fe}]$	13.6	13.7	30.6	31.4	8.7	8.7
$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Co}]$	11.6	11.6	37.9	37.9	—	—
$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Ni}]$	16.4	16.4	35.8	35.8	—	—
$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Cu}]$	17.5	17.5	35.4	35.4	—	—

R→CH₃, (CH₃)₂

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MEASUREMENTS

Complex	Temp. K°	X _M × 10 ⁻⁶ c.g.s. units	μ _{eff} Found	(B.M.) Calc.	n	Hybridization	Stereo-Chemistry
$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Fe}]$	302	14894	5.99	5.92	5	sp ³ d ²	High spin octahedral
$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Co}]$	302	Diamagnetic	0	0	0	d ² sp ³	Low spin octahedral
$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Ni}]$	302	Diamagnetic	0	0	0	dsp ²	Square planar
$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Cu}]$	302	10717	1.69	1.73	1	dsp ²	Square planar

n = number of unpaired electrons.

TABLE 3—INFRARED FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) AND THEIR ASSIGNMENTS
Absorption bands (cm⁻¹)

PNBX	$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Fe}]$	$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Co}]$	$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Ni}]$	$[(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Cu}]$	Assignments
1060(s)	1020(s)	1040(s)	1028(s)	1030(s)	C=S (sulphur is involved)
1090(s)	1120(s)	1125(m)	1120(s)	1118(s)	C—O—C (oxygen is not involved)
1160(s)	1216(s)	1200(sb)	1215(m)	1190(s)	
—	1630(sb), 3300-3200(sb).	—	—	—	H ₂ O present

s = sharp, m = medium, sb = sharp broad.

from the resulting solutions. These were kept overnight, filtered and dried on filter papers. The solid products were then recrystallised with benzene [Fe(III), Ni(II), Co(II)-complexes] and with acetone [Cu-complex], under reduced pressure, and dried in vacuum desiccator. The isolated complexes were subjected to chemical analysis for metal and sulphur. The iron complex was also analysed for chloride ion. The results are given in Table 1.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out with the help of Gouy's magnetic balance having a semimicrometer balance, model C Mettlov Zoric type H_{1.6} No. 140050 at 29°. The observed molar susceptibilities were corrected for diamagnetic contributions. The results are given in Table 2.

Infrared spectrum of Fe(III), Co(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes of PNBX were taken in KBr medium by the method of fast scanning using 'Beckman I.R. 20'. The principal assignments for respective metal complexes and ligand are given in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

Conductometric titrations show sharp breaks corresponding to the metal : ligand ratios of 1 : 2

for Fe(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) and 1 : 3 for Co(III). The ratios are further supported by the results of the amperometric titrations which were carried out on the plateau of PNBX which gave an anodic wave. These results were confirmed by the results of chemical analysis (Table 1).

The results of the magnetic measurements presented in Table 2 throw light on the stereo-chemistry of these complexes. The magnetic moment for the Fe(III) complex, $[\text{Fe}(\text{ROCS}_2)_2\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ was found to be 5.99 B.M. which is in fair agreement for high spin (sp³d²) octahedral Fe(III) complexes^{5,6}.

The cobalt complex, $[\text{Co}(\text{ROCS}_2)_2]$ was found to be diamagnetic which is in agreement with the behaviour exhibited by low spin (d²sp³) cobalt(III) complexes⁷⁻⁹. This also indicates that Co(II) changes to Co(III) during complexation. Ligands containing the CS₂ moiety are known to form stable Co(III) complexes and generally the Co(II) complexes, if formed, are difficult to isolate.

The Ni(II) complex, $[\text{Ni}(\text{ROCS}_2)_2]$ was found to be diamagnetic while the Cu(II) complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{ROCS}_2)_2]$ showed a magnetic moment of 1.69 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired spin. This indicates a square planar configuration^{10,11} (dsp²) for both the Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes.

In the infrared spectrum of PNBX, the C-O-C absorption bands appeared at 1090 cm^{-1} and 1160 cm^{-1} , whereas in *n*-butyl xanthato-complexes of Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II), the C-O-C absorption bands were observed at 1120 cm^{-1} and 1216 cm^{-1} ; 1125 cm^{-1} and 1200 cm^{-1} ; 1120 cm^{-1} and 1215 cm^{-1} ; 1118 cm^{-1} and 1190 cm^{-1} ; respectively. These observations were in accord with the findings of Little *et al.*^{1,2} who had shown that in xanthato-complexes, the C-O-C stretching frequencies appeared in the region $1110\text{--}1140\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 1200 cm^{-1} whereas the frequency of C-O-C band in alkyl xanthates were observed in the lower region. The observations under discussion indicated non-participation of oxygen of C-O-C in bonding with metals.

In the infrared spectrum of potassium *n*-butyl xanthate the C=S stretching frequency band appeared at 1060 cm^{-1} . Little *et al.* (loc cit.) had reported that in xanthato-complexes the C=S stretching band appeared at $1020\text{--}1070\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the i.r. spectra of Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes with PNBX, the C=S stretching band appeared at 1020 cm^{-1} , 1040 cm^{-1} , 1028 cm^{-1} and 1030 cm^{-1} , respectively. The lowering of the frequency of C=S band in *n*-butyl xanthato-complexes indicated involvement of sulphur in bonding with the metals.

Furthermore in the i.r. spectrum of Fe(III)-PNBX complex, the appearance of a broad absorption band in the region $3000\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a sharp band at 1630 cm^{-1} , was a strong evidence for the presence of water molecule in the complex.

On the basis of spectral, magnetic and other studies the following structures could be assigned to these metal complexes

(M-NBX)
M = Ni(II) & Cu(II)

[Fe(III)-NBX]

Structure and Mechanism for Co(III) Complex Formation :

Ordinarily the Co(II) complex should also give the metal-ligand stoichiometric ratio of 1 : 2. But since the physical methods, chemical analysis and magnetic measurement, all provided evidence for the Co(III) complex, it might be inferred that the complex formation was accompanied by simultaneous oxidation of the unstable reaction product. As such the following steps could be written for the reaction :

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